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D3.4 – Communication APP demonstrator

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Deliverable Leader	Engineering Ingegneria Informatica (ENG)
Deliverable coordinator	Vladimiro Scotto di Carlo (ENG) – vladimiro.scottodicarlo@eng.it
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1.1. Author

Author name	Organization Acr.	E-mail
Vladimiro Scotto di Carlo	ENG	vladimiro.scottodicarlo@eng.it

1.2. Contributors

Contributor name	Organization Acr.	E-mail

1.3. Reviewers

Reviewers name	Organization Acr.	E-mail
Thomas Oikonomou	ELLINOGERMANIKI	thoikonomou@ea.gr
Teuvo Uusitalo	VTT	teuvo.uusitalo@vtt.fi

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Editor address data	Name: Vladimiro Scotto di Carlo Partner: ENG Address: Torre Saverio Isola C1 Centro Direzionale, 80143 Napoli Phone: +393479022570 Email: vladimiro.scottodicarlo@eng.it
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1.7. Acronyms

Acronym	Description
API	Application Programming Interface
GiB	Gibibyte, 2 ³⁰ byte (not to be confused with Gigabyte)
EBS	Elastic Block Store, cloud block storage for virtual machines on Amazon cloud platform
EU	European Union
MERN	MongoDB, Express, React, Node
PU	Public Document
REST	REpresentation State Transfer
UI	User Interface
vCPU	Virtual CPU
WCAG	Web Content Accessibility Guidelines
WebGL	Web-based Graphics Library
WP	Work Package

2. Introduction

2.1. Deliverable Aims and Objectives

The Deliverable D3.4 is a digital demonstrator. It is therefore a piece of software that provides specific features to users that has been developed and made available for project activities.

So this document does not constitute the deliverable, but it is a companion document that explains the technology, architecture and main functions of the demonstrator.

2.2. Project Overview

GreenSCENT – Smart Citizen Education for a Green Future – is a research and innovation project funded by the European Union's Horizon 2020 programme, under Grant Agreement N° 101036480.

The primary objective of GreenSCENT is to support the implementation of Green Deal policies by engaging EU citizens, particularly young people, in the co-creation, testing, and validation of a European Multidisciplinary Competence Framework that encompasses the main thematic areas of the EU Green Deal. The project aims to foster acceptance and uptake of the Green Deal through a multi-stakeholder participatory approach and measure its effectiveness in terms of awareness, skills, and implicit attitudes, which are crucial for real behavioural change.

The main founding pillars of the GreenSCENT project are as follows:

- **Citizen Engagement:** Within the project, citizen engagement is considered a driver for change. Actively involving citizens in policymaking improves the effectiveness, quality, and uptake of policies and decisions addressing complex challenges at both global and local levels, ranging from climate change to welfare redesign, territorial development, or public service provision. When citizens are involved and feel included in the creation of innovations, rather than merely being recipients, it becomes easier to ensure broad acceptance of these innovations.
- **Active Experimentation:** Active observation, data collection, and open innovation can enhance understanding and increase acceptance. By promoting engagement and hands-on actions, individuals are motivated to participate and feel involved in addressing environmental problems primarily caused by human activities. GreenSCENT will offer various comprehensive "demonstrators" that allow students and citizens to apply the proposed competency framework, encouraging them to engage with science and their behaviour. This way, they can observe, understand, and evaluate the impact of their actions on the planet.
- **European Youth:** The youth of the European Union is crucial for promoting knowledge and information about the Green Deal and the importance of adopting green behaviours. Young EU citizens can disseminate this information to their peers both in and out of school, as well as to their families. As they grow, they can become professionals driving change in the workforce, various industries, political, and social processes, all towards a green perspective for the planet's protection. Educational institutions like schools and universities play a vital role in this process. GreenSCENT plans to showcase its demonstrators in various settings, including schools, universities, and non-formal education settings, such as Open Innovation Challenges and Citizen Engagement initiatives, across different educational levels.
- **Involvement of Vulnerable Groups:** It is important to involve vulnerable groups, including migrants, refugees, people with disabilities, the elderly, and those living in rural areas, in both discussions and

practical measures concerning the Green Deal. The European Union's "united in diversity" philosophy cannot be achieved if these groups are excluded. Respect for diversity, inclusion, and democratic participation are fundamental EU principles, and GreenSCENT will ensure these are upheld. Considering the changes in education post-COVID-19, new methods of engaging people are necessary, and digital accessibility is crucial. Creating accessible content is essential to reach and motivate people while minimizing the risk of dropping out of education. GreenSCENT will involve different user groups in designing and validating proposed solutions and will adopt accessibility standards and cross-cultural approaches in developing any analog or digital demonstrators supporting the GreenSCENT Competence Framework.

- **GreenSCENT Competence Framework: Acceptance and Adoption:** The GreenSCENT project aims to involve EU citizens in increasing awareness and acceptance of the Green Deal growth plan. In addition to citizens, the project will engage potential users and stakeholders of the Competence Framework, such as experts, activists, educational providers, and employers. This engagement is necessary to ensure the broad adoption of the GreenSCENT Competence Framework beyond the project's lifetime. The framework can be used as a tool for designing and implementing educational initiatives both inside and outside the classroom. It can also facilitate the integration of environmental-related competencies in human resources and talent management enterprise processes.
- **Additional Competences Beyond Climate and Environment:** The project will involve citizens, particularly students, in activities that aim to test and validate the proposed competence framework. These activities will help individuals develop various competencies beyond just climate and sustainability knowledge. For instance, they will be challenged in areas such as science education, digital competences, and soft skills like creative thinking, problem-solving, team working, project planning, and design. These transversal and complementary competencies will positively impact both their personal and professional capacities, as well as their understanding of climate and environmental challenges.

3. General information about demonstrator

3.1. General Architecture

The Communication App, also known as the Environmental Monitoring App is, a non-native web app that operates through the native browser of the smartphone (Safari on iOS, Chrome on Android). This means that it is not an app developed natively for iOS and Android, and therefore it does not need to be distributed on the App Store and Google Play Store. Instead, it is a mobile web interface that behaves like an app and must be visualized through the smartphone's browser engine. It has been designed as a seamless pipeline that can effectively store and manage various types of multimedia **content**, including **video, photos, documents, and data**, all of which are generated by or made available by the users of the platform.

The *Figure 1* provides an overview of the entire GreenSCENT platform, highlighting its core components and how they interconnect. The architecture comprises:

- The central Storage and distribution facility
- The Environmental Mobile APP
- The Interactive Documentaries tool
- The Citizen Journalism tool
- The administration Interface for overall platform management

This diagram serves as a visual guide to the platform's structure, showcasing the Environmental Monitoring Mobile App as the primary interface for user input.

When users submit a new environmental report, the mobile app communicates with the platform via a set of RESTful APIs (an Application Programming Interface that conforms to the design principles of the REpresentational State Transfer architectural style), allowing for immediate data transmission and storage. Once stored, the report is ready for further action.

The mobile application enables registered users to create detailed environmental reports, which includes a title, an in-depth description, and visual documentation through photos or videos. Each report is geotagged and categorized according to urgency levels, such as Risk, Emergency, Pollution, and Solution. Additionally, the application displays all submitted reports on a map, pinpointed by their geographic coordinates.

The GreenSCENT Environmental Monitoring Mobile App is tailored to collect environmental observations from citizens. It can effectively show, store and manage various types of geolocated reports that can include multimedia content (e.g. video, photos, documents, and text) generated by or made available by the users of the GreenSCENT platform. Geolocation is crucial feature of the app, requiring users to grant access to their geographic location.

Once logged in with institutional credentials, the app allows students and teachers to submit new environmental reports and track existing ones.

Institutions can use the app to compile reports submitted by authenticated users. Each report undergoes an approval or rejection process by the institution's administrator to ensure relevance and prevent duplication or inconsistency.

Figure 1 – GreenSCENT Platform overall architecture

The GreenSCENT web/mobile platform, encompassing the Web Admin interface, the Web User interface, and the Environmental Monitoring App, is a **robust web application compatible with all major web browsers**, including Google Chrome, Mozilla Firefox, Safari, and any others that **support the HTML 5 and WebGL standards**. It has been developed with the MERN stack (MongoDB, Express, React, Node, see *Figure 2*), this open-source middleware stack enables the creation of dynamic web and mobile interfaces that seamlessly communicate with a sophisticated backend system.

Figure 2 – MERN stack (source: bigscal.com)

The platform is designed according to the **three-tier architecture model** (see *Figure 3*), which includes:

- **Presentation Layer:** The user-facing frontend interface.
- **Application Layer:** The core business logic of the application.
- **Database Layer:** The data storage and management component.

This structure ensures a unified and efficient system, enhancing user experience by clearly delineating responsibilities across each layer for streamlined and user-friendly interactions.

Figure 3 - Tier architecture convention

3.2. Hardware requirements for the overall platform

The backend part (Application Layer and Database layer) has been deployed on a cloud server under the responsibility of ENG. The server is a virtual machine on the Amazon AWS cloud infrastructure. The venue of the server farm is located in Milan and all the cloud resources are inside EU territory.

The server used is part of the t3 family (general purpose workloads based on 2nd generation Intel Xeon Platinum 8000 series processor). The specific instance allocated for the project is t3.xlarge (4vCPU, 16 GiB). The operative system is Oracle Linux 8.5. Currently the server has 300 GB SSD disk on EBS. Hardware characteristics can be increased/improved as needed. For instance, the number of vCPU or the RAM of the instance, or the disk space.

3.3. System requirements for users

Mobile operative system Requirements

Android smartphone with Android 8.0 (Oreo) or more recent

or

iPhone with iOS 11 or more recent

Browser Requirements

- Chrome browser on Android device.
- Safari browser on iOS device.

Internet Requirements

A fast internet connection of at least 30 Mbps is strongly recommended.

4. Main Features

4.1. Download and Installation

Feature	
Description	How to install the app (Android phones)
Link to demonstrator	https://greenscent-app.net/ or QR Code
Tutorial	<p>To install the mobile app on an Android device:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Open the Chrome browser on your Android device and enter the following URL: https://greenscent-app.net/ or frame the QR Code. 2. Once the page has loaded, look for the icon to access a list of options. 3. Among the options, find and select 'Install App' to initiate the installation process on your device. 4. Follow the on-screen prompts to complete the installation. 5. After the installation is complete, you should see the GreenSCENT icon on your device's main screen.

Feature	
Description	How to install the app (iPhones)
Link to demonstrator	https://greenscent-app.net/ or QR code
Tutorial	<p>To install the mobile app on an iOS device:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Launch the Safari browser on your iOS device and navigate to the URL https://greenscent-app.net/ or frame the QR code. • Locate the button and tap on it to reveal additional options. • From the options presented, choose "Add to Home Screen." • A popup will appear; tap "Add" in the top right corner to confirm and complete the GreenSCENT installation on your iOS device.

4.2. Enabling Geolocation

Feature	
Description	Enabling Geolocation (Android)
Tutorial	The app requires the authorization to access the GPS position of the device. The procedure on Android devices is very simple. When the app is launched for the first time a dialog box is opened asking the user to authorize geolocation (see <i>Figure 5</i>).

Figure 5 – Enabling Geolocation (Android)

Feature	
Description	Enabling Geolocation (iPhone)
Tutorial	<p>The app requires the authorization to access the GPS position of the device. Before the app is launched follow the procedure:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ensure that the GreenSCENT app is NOT currently running. • Go to Settings > Safari>Location and confirm that Allow option is set. Please be aware that, to the best of our knowledge, if this option is not accessible, it likely means that Parental Controls have been activated, preventing geolocation. In such a case, you won't be able to use the app to report issues. • Go to Settings > Privacy & Security > Location Services and make sure that Location Services is on. • Still in Settings > Privacy & Security > Location Services scroll down to find the app “Safari”. • Tap the app “Safari” and select an option “Always”.

4.3. Selection of the institution

Feature	
Description	The landing page of the app (even before authentication) asks the users to select the institution they belong to. It's impossible to complete authentication without the correct selection of the institution.
Tutorial	Launch the app With a horizontal swipe movement, users can see all the available institutions (see <i>Figure 6</i>).

Figure 6 – Selection of the institution

They will have to choose one and tap it.

Currently the available domains are:

- DBT. Danish Board of Technology
- EA. Ellinogermaniki Agogi
- ENGLAB. Engineering test instance
- MAYK. Maunulan yhteiskoulu ja Helsingin matematiikkalukio
- RYT. Royal School of Transylvania
- SMART. Gimnazija Smart
- TEST. Generic test instance
- UAB. Universitat Autònoma de Barcelona
- UNIPILO
- UNIRSM. Università della Repubblica di San Marino
- UNISPMF. University of Novi Sad
- VOLENS

4.4. Login

Feature	
Description	How to access to the web platform with the institutional login credentials
Tutorial	On the navigation bar on the top of the screen there is a padlock. Clicking on the padlock users can authenticate and get full access to the features of the app (see <i>Figure 7</i>).

4.5. List View

Feature	
Description	Description of the default interface of the app
Tutorial	The List VIEW serves as the default interface, displaying all reports submitted within the area as a sequence of cards. Each card corresponds to an individual report, with the arrangement following a chronological order from the oldest to the most recent (see <i>Figure 8</i>).

Figure 8 – Main Page

At the top of the page, there is a horizontally scrollable list of tags. These tags denote the **categories** managed **by the platform** and can be tapped to filter and display only the reports belonging to a selected category (see *Figure 9*). The active categories are:

- **#RISK**
- **#EMERGENCY**
- **#POLLUTION**
- **#SOLUTION**

Figure 9 – List of tags

Beneath the tag list lies a vertically scrollable list of cards, where each card represents a distinct report (see *Figure 10*).

Figure 10 – Report

Essential details presented on each card include:

- **Owner’s Avatar** (the avatar of the user who has submitted the report)
- **Report State Icon:** Approved
- **Title of the report**
- **Date and Time** of Submission
- **Distance** from the user’s Current Location to the reported issue (does not work if GPS is not active)

To obtain more details about a report, tap on its corresponding card. Further information is provided in the subsequent sections.

4.6. Map View

Feature	
Description	Description of the Map View of the app
Tutorial	<p>The Map View can be accessed by clicking the designated button on the navigation bar located at the bottom of the page (see <i>Figure 11</i>). This view allows users to see the submitted reports represented as markers on a map.</p> <div data-bbox="726 1305 1189 1370" data-label="Image"> </div> <p style="text-align: center;"><i>Figure 11 – Navigation bar</i></p> <p>Key functionalities of the Map View include:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Interactive Map: Users can smoothly scroll and use pinch-to-zoom to navigate the map. • Customisable View: The map can be resized and moved according to user preferences. • Report List: A horizontally scrollable list of reports is integrated into the map. • Report Details: Tapping on any map marker will reveal the corresponding report’s card. • Direct Access: Each report card is tappable providing access to the report details. • Report Identification: The selected report is highlighted with a red-outlined marker. • User Location: A green pinpoint marks the user’s current location.

Figure 12 – Geographical representation (Map View) of the reports

4.7. Report detail

Feature	
Description	How to see the detail of a report
Tutorial	To view the detailed information of a report, tap on a report card either in the LIST view or the MAP view (see Figure 13). This action will open the report detail dialog page.

Figure 14 – Detail of a report

The detail page includes:

- **Owner/Creator:** Displays the avatar with name next to it.
- **Dates:** Shows both the **creation** and the most recent **update date**.
- **Title:** The heading of the report.
- **Tags:** Used for classification purposes.
- **Severity Level:** Indicated as low, medium, or high.
- **Problem Description:** A detailed account of the issue reported.

4.8. See the photos attached to the report

Feature	
Description	How to see the photo gallery that have been attached to the report
Tutorial	To view the photo and video gallery associated with a report, navigate to the report’s detail page. Here, you will find the gallery that was attached when report was initially created (see <i>Figure 15</i>).

Figure 15 – Photo gallery

4.9. Navigation turn by turn to reach the place of report

Feature	
Description	How to activate the navigation turn by turn to reach the place of a report
Tutorial	On the detail page you can view the current distance to the report’s location. By clicking the icon, you can open the native navigation app (Google Maps or Apple Maps) with the route already set from your current position to the report’s location (see <i>Figure 16</i>).

Figure 16 – Navigation turn by turn

4.10. Insert New Report

Feature	
Description	How insert a new report
Tutorial	Any authenticated user can add a new report to the institution's collection. Such reports must be approved by an administrator before they are visible to other users. In the app select the New section in the bottom navigation bar (see <i>Figure 17</i>).

Figure 17 – Create a new report

On the "Create Report" page, fill in the necessary details:

- **Title:** Enter a brief title for quick identification.
- **Description:** Provide a detailed description of the issue.
- **Severity:** Choose the appropriate severity level using the radio buttons provided.
- **Tags:** Select relevant tags for the report.
- **Upload Multimedia:** Use the "UPLOAD MULTIMEDIA" button to add photos or videos, setting one as the main image. Repeat this step to add multiple media files.
- **Location:** Use the "CURRENT" button to use your current location for the report, or "ON MAP" to choose a different location. The GPS coordinates will be displayed next to the "GPS POSITION" label.

Once all information is entered, click the **"SEND"** button to submit the report. It will appear in the app PERSONAL folder and the **"Citizen Journalism"** section on the GreenVERSE web portal. Note that the report must be approved by an administrator before it becomes visible to other users (see the next section for details).

4.11. New Report approval/rejection

Feature	
Description	Approval or rejection of new reports
Tutorial	<p>To manage the approval or rejection of new reports using the Citizen Journalism web tool, administrators should follow these steps:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Go To http://greenvrerse.net • Click on the "LOGIN" icon located in the top right corner of the homepage (see Figure 18) to access the login page. <div data-bbox="563 920 1358 1328" data-label="Image"> </div> <p style="text-align: center;"><i>Figure 18 – Login page.</i></p> <p>On the login page, enter the following credentials:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Username: Type your email in the "EMAIL" field (note that this field is case sensitive, even though mail addresses are not). - Password :Enter your password in the "PASSWORD" field. - Institution: Select your institution name from the "SELECT INSTITUTION" dropdown list. <p>After logging in, you will be directed to the Landing page (see</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Figure 19</i>). Here click on the Citizen Journalism section.

Figure 19 – Homepage of the web interface

- In the Citizen Journalism section (see *Figure 20*), you will see a list of report cards. Select the report you wish to evaluate and click on the menu in the top-right corner of the card.

Figure 20 – Citizen Journalism list of reports

- Choose CHANGE STATUS from the menu options (see *Figure 21*).

Figure 21 – CHANGE STATUS

- In the dialog box, set the status to either APPROVED or REJECTED.

Confirm the status by clicking the "SAVE" button.

4.12. Registration of new users

Feature	Registration of new users
<p>Description</p>	<p>Registration of new users</p>
<p>Tutorial</p>	<p>On the login page, a new user has the option to register for the platform. Once the institution is selected, the user may proceed with the standard login procedure by clicking on the Register link (see <i>Figure 22</i>).</p> <p style="text-align: center;"><i>Figure 22 – Registration of new users from the app</i></p> <p>The form requires users to fill in</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - nickname, - email, - password, - confirmation of the password. <p>After submitting their registration request, users are required to wait for the administrator to verify and approve it through the platform’s web interface. The administrator will either approve or reject the request. Approved users will gain access to the portal and its features. Conversely, users whose requests are rejected will be unable to access the portal.</p> <p>The process to approve or reject a user is conducted via the Greenverse platform. Administrator must login at http://greenverse.net. Upon successful login, all sections of the main landing page become accessible, and the user’s avatar is displayed on the top right corner ribbon.</p> <p>The administrator now must click on the SETTINGS button (see <i>Figure 23</i>).</p>

Figure 23 – Homepage of the web interface, SETTINGS

And on the USERS tab

Figure 24 – SETTINGS page on the web interface

The administrator will see all the users of the institution registered to the platform(see Figure 25). The ones yet to be approved will be shown in red.

Figure 25 – List of users in the SETTINGS section of the web interface

Clicking on the red pen, the administrator can see a dialog that allows the approval (or rejection) of the user (see

Figure 26).

Figure 26 – Approval/rejection feature in the SETTINGS section of the web interface

4.13. How to see all the reports

Feature	
Description	To view all reports you have created, regardless of their status (TO BE APPROVED, APPROVED and SOLVED) follow these steps.
Tutorial	<p>Access the view that displays only the reports you have created. This includes reports pending approval and those already solved. You can perform certain actions depending on the report's status:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Remove a report if it is in the TO BE APPROVED status. • Mark a report as SOLVED if it is in the APPROVED status. <p>The interface resembles the LIST VIEW and each report represented as a card (see Figure 27).</p> <p>To open and view a report's details, simply tap on its card.</p>

Figure 27 – List of reports belonging to the signed in user

4.14. How to start a social interaction on a report

Feature	
Description	How to start a social interaction on a report
Tutorial	<p>From the detail page you can get access to the social section of the app that allows users to comment a report posting updates about the situation (see <i>Figure 28</i>).</p> <div data-bbox="491 725 1430 1554" style="text-align: center;"> </div>

Figure 28 – Social interaction on a report via app

By clicking the REPLY button (see *Figure 29*), users can respond to the initial description. This action initiates a thread of comments where users can post updates, seek additional information, share insights, or add further photographic evidence.

Figure 29 – Reply to a report

- To add a photograph, follow the procedure

Figure 30 – Add a photograph to a report